

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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METHODS FOR ASSESSING FINANCIAL-ECONOMIC SECURITY OF ENTERPRISES OF THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTER

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the in-depth study of the methods of assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises. It explains the need to ensure the economic security of enterprises and its importance. Also, factors affecting economic security, risks and threats related to them are identified. In the article, financial stability of enterprises, efficiency of production processes, level of resource utilization and indicators of flexibility to market conditions are presented as the main aspects of evaluation. Methods such as statistical analysis, expert assessment and econometric modeling are used in the research, and a comprehensive approach to determining the level of economic security of industrial enterprises is proposed. The author develops scientific and practical recommendations for increasing the stability of industrial enterprises and ensuring their economic security. This article is useful for managers of industrial enterprises, economists and researchers, and serves to develop effective strategies for increasing economic security.

Key words: Industrial enterprises, economic security, cluster, assessment methods, financial stability, risks, strategic planning, statistical analysis, econometric modeling, risk management, analytical methods, financial control.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola sanoat korxonalarining iqtisodiy xavfsizligini baholash usullarini chuqur o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Unda korxonalarining iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlash zarurati va uning ahamiyati batafsil tushuntiriladi. Shuningdek, iqtisodiy xavfsizlikka ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar, xavf-xatarlar va ularning tahlikalari aniqlanadi. Maqolada korxonalar moliyaviy barqarorligi, ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarining samaradorligi, resurslardan foydalanish darajasi va bozor sharoitlariga moslashuvchanlik kabi ko'rsatkichlar baholashning asosiy jihatlari sifatida keltirilgan. Tadqiqotda statistik tahlil, ekspert baholash va ekonometriya modellashtirish kabi usullar qo'llanilib, sanoat korxonalarining iqtisodiy xavfsizlik darajasini aniqlash uchun kompleks yondashuv taklif etiladi. Muallif sanoat korxonalarining barqarorligini oshirish va ularning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha ilmiy va amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqadi. Ushbu maqola sanoat korxonalarini rahbarlari, iqtisodchilar va tadqiqotchilar uchun foydali bo'lib, iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni oshirishga qaratilgan samarali strategiyalarni ishlab chiqishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: sanoat korxonalarini, iqtisodiy xavfsizlik, klaster, baholash usullari, moliyaviy barqarorlik, xavf-xatarlar, strategik rejalashtirish, statistik tahlil, ekonometriya modellashtirish, xavfni boshqarish, analitik usullar, moliyaviy nazorat.

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена глубокому изучению методов оценки экономической безопасности промышленных предприятий. В ней объясняется необходимость обеспечения экономической безопасности предприятий и её значение. Также определяются факторы, влияющие на экономическую безопасность, риски и связанные с ними угрозы. В статье представлены такие основные аспекты оценки, как финансовая устойчивость предприятий, эффективность производственных процессов, уровень использования ресурсов и показатели гибкости к рыночным условиям. В исследовании используются методы статистического анализа, экспертной оценки и эконометрического моделирования, а также предлагается комплексный подход к определению уровня экономической безопасности промышленных предприятий. Автор разрабатывает научные и практические рекомендации по повышению устойчивости промышленных предприятий и обеспечению их экономической безопасности. Эта статья полезна для руководителей промышленных предприятий, экономистов и исследователей, а также служит развитию эффективных стратегий повышения экономической безопасности.

Ключевые слова: промышленные предприятия, экономическая безопасность, кластер, методы оценки, финансовая устойчивость, риски, стратегическое планирование, статистический анализ, эконометрическое моделирование, управление рисками, аналитические методы, финансовый контроль.

INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of today's globalization and digitalization of economy, ensuring the economic security of industrial enterprises is important not only for the stable development of the enterprise, but also for the national economy as a whole. Economic security represents the ability of the enterprise to effectively manage financial, production, investment and other resources and maintain its competitiveness in market conditions. This article examines the methods of assessing the economic security of enterprises within the industrial cluster, identifies important criteria and analysis tools.

Economic security issues are studied at different levels of the economic system, including being the subject of microeconomic analysis, since for enterprises ensuring economic security is the key to survival in conditions of aggravation of political and socio-economic contradictions in world markets, incomplete legal protection and corruption within the country, as well as many other external and internal threats. Information as a set of data on the state and changes in the internal and external environment in the economic security system of the enterprise is used to study, evaluate and analyse economic phenomena and processes in order to develop and make managerial decisions to ensure the level of security necessary for the existence and development. The economic security management of the enterprise is a continuous process (from the foundation to the liquidation of the enterprise) of monitoring the operational environment in order to identify the influence of all factors on the security level as the basis for the development, implementation and control of each management decision within the enterprise.

Methods of assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises are necessary to improve the financial and operational status of the enterprise, to ensure its continued development, and to protect it from various risks. These methods help to determine how efficiently the enterprise is performing its activities and how it maintains its position in the market.

With the help of economic security assessment methods, the enterprise examines its financial situation, production processes and how it uses resources. This allows to determine what risks threaten the enterprise. For example, factors such as market changes, economic crises or competitors' activities can harm the enterprise. Therefore, with the help of these methods, the enterprise can analyze its strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and risks, and develop strategies against them.

In addition, through methods of assessing the economic security of enterprises within the industrial cluster, investors and other interested parties can be assured. Through these methods, the enterprises of cluster can demonstrate its financial strength, competitiveness and flexibility to market requirements. Thus, the methods of assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises serve not only to improve internal management processes, but also to ensure the long-term success of the enterprise.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The issue of ensuring and assessing the safety of the enterprise today is one of the important objects of research by many scientists (Franchuk et al., 2020; O. Biliomistniy, I. Bilomistna, & Galushko, 2017; Burkaltseva et al., 2017; Britchenko et al., 2018) [1]. Modern scientific researches of problems of providing and assessing the security of the enterprise have significantly expanded and cover more and more components of the economic security itself. For example, Sytkin et al. (2019) [2] and Wu and Meng (2019) [3] determined the place and role of management in the context of security. In terms of economic security, its formation and organizational support have been investigated by Khalina et al. (2019) [4].

There are many definitions and approaches to the economic security of the enterprise. For example, according to D.M. Dryagunov [5], the economic security of an enterprise should be understood as a certain situation in which its stable supply of financial, material and other resources is ensured for its operation and profit [5]. Another scientist, A.D. Sheremet [6], understands the economic security of the enterprise as the state in which all resources are used most effectively to neutralize emerging threats, as well as to ensure its continuous operation for a long time. According to V.L. Shults, the economic security of any enterprise is a certain state, the main goal of which is to provide protection from various threats that negatively affect its activity [7].

From the point of view of V.K. Senchagov, a Russian scientist, the economic security of the enterprise is defined as a set of measures that includes a combination of factors, does not depend only on the internal situation, the impact of the enterprise's external environment, and measures taken by the enterprise against economic threats.

A.H. Glyumov [8] and E.P. Kiselitsy stated that the economic security of the enterprise is characterized by the sum of qualitative and quantitative economic security indicators, the main of which is determined by evaluating the state of using the resources of the enterprise according to economic security criteria. They say

that the economic security of the enterprise is characterized by a combination of qualitative and quantitative indicators, the main of which is the level of economic security of the enterprise is determined by evaluating the state of using the resources of the enterprise according to the criteria of economic security.

I.N. Dyshlova and V.A. Lukyanenko define the economic security of an enterprise as a state when “it can successfully carry out its activities, while being economically and financially stable, as well as develop its position in the future” [9].

Khudoley O.V. [10] defines the economic security of an enterprise as “the ability to use resources as efficiently as possible in the present and future, to maintain a stable, balanced state, despite many external and internal destabilizing factors”. At the same time, the author tried to reflect the need to take into account internal and external threats, the priority of strategic goals for the development of the enterprise and the role of efficient resource consumption in the process of achieving them.

Sitdikova and Starodumova [11] in the context of assessing economic security, examined the main corporate problems that may arise in ensuring security. Kljucnikov, Mura, and Sklenar [12] examined information support for security and how to protect information related to the economic activity of an enterprise. Avanesova et al. made a good contribution to the development of security assurance and assessment in business organizations in the context of preventing an economic crisis [13]. An important component of economic security and its financial component, without which it is impossible to effectively assess its condition. In more detail, it was the financial aspect of economic security that Farber investigated [14].

In addition to the approaches briefly described above, others are known, but they are a certain combination of those already considered, or not yet received wide distribution and recognition in the scientific community. In addition to the essence of each of the approaches, we consider it appropriate to note that their application is characterized by a number of disadvantages.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the course of the research, scientific studies on the methods of assessing the economic security of enterprises of industrial clusters were studied. Observation and selection, scientific-theoretical, empirical observation methods were used in the process of creating the article. The reliability of the research results is explained by the use of foreign and national statistical official sources used in the research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Economic security is the protection of the enterprise from external and internal threats and the ability to create the necessary conditions for sustainable economic development. The economic security of enterprises of the industrial cluster mainly depends on the following factors (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Factors determining the economic security of industrial enterprises¹.

¹ It was prepared by the author based on information from Internet sources and scientific literature

Comprehensive consideration of the above-mentioned factors and establishment of effective management is one of the main conditions for ensuring the economic security of industrial enterprises.

Assessing the economic security of enterprises of the industrial cluster is the process of determining whether the enterprise is protected from threats in the external and internal environment, studying the level of effective use of resources, and analyzing the possibilities of ensuring its stable operation. This assessment is aimed at determining the financial stability of the enterprise, production efficiency, market competitiveness and the quality of the risk management system.

The aim of assessing the economic security is to ensure the stability of the enterprises within the cluster against internal and external threats, to maintain its financial and operational stability, as well as to ensure long-term competitiveness. The main aim of assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises (Fig. 2):

Figure 2. The main purpose of assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises².

The assessment of the economic security of enterprises of the industrial cluster includes a complete and in-depth analysis of the general state of the enterprise, identification of risks, maintaining financial and operational stability, increasing competitiveness and developing long-term development strategies. This process serves to ensure the economic security of the enterprise, to attract new investments and to expand the possibilities of successful operation in the market.

Several main criteria are distinguished in ensuring the economic security of enterprises of the industrial cluster. They represent the economic indicators and aspects necessary for the stable operation and development of the enterprise. The criteria for evaluating the economic security of industrial enterprises is an important indicator in determining the stability, efficiency and resistance to risks of the enterprise. These criteria are necessary for industrial enterprises to operate efficiently, maintain stability and resist various economic, technological and external threats. They allow the enterprise to work successfully in the short and long term [15]. The economic security of enterprises of the industrial cluster is evaluated according to the following main criteria (Table 1):

Table 1. Criteria for assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises.

Evaluation criteria	Composition of types of evaluation criteria
Financial stability	Net profit, revenue and profitability levels; The volume of use of debt funds and the stability of the debt burden; Liquidity indicators of the enterprise (quick, current and total liquidity).
Production efficiency	The level of utilization of production capacity; Product quality and introduction of innovative technologies; Labor productivity and employee efficiency.
Market competitiveness	Market share and product competitiveness; Adaptability to marketing strategies and customer requirements.
Risk Management	Identifying internal and external risks and developing countermeasures; Risks related to tax, exchange rate, inflation and other factors.
Effective use of resources	The level of economical use of tangible and intangible resources; Efficiency of operational processes.

The criteria listed above help to comprehensively assess the economic security of enterprises within the industrial cluster and ensure sustainable development. In the evaluation process, the specific aspects and indicators of each criterion are taken into account. This allows identifying the weaknesses of the enterprise and reducing risks.

² It was prepared by the author based on information from Internet sources and scientific literature

Several methods are used to assess the economic security of industrial enterprises. Financial indicators, economic modeling and expert assessment methods are distinguished among them (Fig. 3):

Figure 3. Methods of assessing the economic security of enterprises of the industrial cluster³.

The main task of the above-mentioned methods of assessing the economic security of industrial enterprises is to determine the financial stability of the enterprise and its adaptability to market conditions. With the help of these methods, the readiness of the industrial cluster against internal and external risks is evaluated and the level of effective use of resources is studied. Let's focus on each of the methods for assessing the economic security of industrial cluster given above:

Evaluation based on financial indicators. Financial stability of the enterprise is one of the main indicators of economic security. This method involves the analysis of enterprise activity according to the following criteria (Table 2):

Table 2. Evaluation methods based on financial indicators⁴.

Liquidity level	Assessment of the ability of the enterprise to cover short-term obligations
Financial independence	Analysis of the company's debt and equity ratio
Profitability	Determining net profit and efficiency of resource utilization
Dynamics of revenue and profit	Tracking changes in revenue and profit indicators

Econometric modeling method. This method allows for a comprehensive analysis of the economic security of the enterprise. Econometric modeling includes:

- Identification and modeling of internal and external factors affecting the enterprise;
- Using statistical methods to predict risks;
- To study the integration between gross production and financial results.

Expert evaluation method. In this method, the level of enterprise security is determined based on the opinions of economists and industry experts. The following processes are carried out during the expert assessment:

- Determining the factors affecting the enterprise's activity.
- Development of economic security criteria.
- Making conclusions by summarizing experts' assessments.

By evaluating the economic security of industrial enterprises, accurate information is provided to the management of the enterprise, which is the basis for making long-term strategic decisions [16]. This process is aimed at ensuring the stability of the company's activities, minimizing financial and operational risks, and increasing competitiveness.

Scientists define the overall level of economic security as the weighted average of current, tactical and strategic security indicators (Formula 1):

$$EcS = \frac{(1)*E+(E)*T_k+(E*T_k)*S}{(1)+(E)+(E*T_k)} \tag{1}$$

3 It was prepared by the author based on information from Internet sources and scientific literature

4 It was prepared by the author based on information from Internet sources and scientific literature

Where EcS is the level of economic security of the enterprise;

(1), (E), (E * T_k) are the coefficients of significance of current, tactical and strategic security, respectively. The level of current, tactical and strategic economic security is determined taking into account formula (2):

$$E(T_k; S) = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^m Z_j * g(\frac{K_j}{N_j})}{\sum_{l=1}^m Z_j} \quad (2)$$

where, E is the level of current economic security of the enterprise;

T_k – the level of tactical economic security of the enterprise;

S – the level of strategic economic security of the enterprise;

Z_j is the coefficient of significance of the jth indicator, determined by an expert method;

K_j is the actual value of the jth indicator;

N_j is the recommended (normative) value of the jth indicator;

m is the number of indicators used to evaluate the corresponding components;

l is the degree, which takes the value 1 if an increase in the value of the indicator indicates an increase in the level of economic security, and -1 if an increase in the value of the indicator negatively affects the safety of the enterprise [17].

To assess the level of economic security of an industrial enterprise, it is necessary to create a system of criteria and indicators that comprehensively characterize and describe its activities [18]. The criteria-based safety assessment should reflect all areas of activity of an industrial enterprise and the main factors from the external environment (Fig. 4):

Figure 4. The basis of the assessment of the level of economic security of the industrial enterprise's spheres of activity based on the criteria⁵

It is advisable to note that only if the indicators are within the acceptable limits of the threshold values, and the achievement of the proper values of some indicators, so as not to occur at the expense of others, it is possible to achieve a high level of economic security in an industrial enterprise [19]. It should be borne in mind that beyond the threshold values of the indicators, an industrial enterprise loses its ability to dynamically develop, competitiveness in domestic and foreign markets and, as a result, is doomed to a reduction in activity, re-profiling or bankruptcy [20].

5 It was prepared by the author based on information from Kopytko M.I. Methodology for assessing the level of economic security of industrial enterprises // Modern management technologies. ISSN 2226-9339. - No. 7 (43). Article number: 4305. Publication date: 08.07.2014. Access mode: <https://sovman.ru/article/4305/>

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, ensuring the economic security of enterprises of the industrial cluster is an important task in the modern economy, because it is related to the competitiveness and sustainable development of enterprises. The results of the research show that the following factors are crucial in ensuring economic security for enterprises of industrial clusters: financial stability, production efficiency, economical use of resources, flexibility to market conditions, introduction of innovations and risk management [21]. The correct assessment of these factors and the development of strategies based on them ensure the long-term success.

We offer the following suggestions for improving the methods of assessing the economic security of enterprises within industrial clusters [22]:

Increasing financial stability: To ensure the economic security of the enterprise, first of all, it is necessary to strengthen financial stability. For this, it is necessary for enterprises to balance their income and expenses, to regularly monitor the level of liquidity and profitability.

Development of innovations: Industrial enterprises should pay attention to the introduction of new technologies to increase their competitiveness. Innovative projects increase the production efficiency of the enterprise and optimize the use of resources.

Implementation of the risk management system: Special systems should be developed for early identification and management of financial and operational risks in enterprises. These systems serve to protect the enterprise from unexpected threats and maintain financial stability.

Expanding the use of analytical methods: Industrial enterprises should use advanced methods in analyzing their activities. For example, with the help of econometric models, the factors affecting the performance of the enterprise should be studied and the information on the basis of strategic planning should be formed.

Strengthen strategic planning: It is necessary to pay special attention to the development and implementation of long-term development strategies in enterprises. Through strategic planning, resources can be used efficiently and flexibility to market demands can be increased.

Training of personnel: In the process of ensuring economic security in enterprises, the participation of highly qualified specialists is important. Therefore, it is recommended to organize permanent training programs for the development of knowledge and skills of employees.

Implementation of the above proposals will help to ensure economic security of enterprises within the industrial clusters, increase their stability and successful operation in market conditions. At the same time, ensuring economic security has a positive effect on the development of the national economy.

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